

From Formality to Substance: Gender-Responsive Budgeting Reform through Village Fiscal Incentives

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the low allocation of budgets for women's empowerment at the village level, which reflects the weak implementation of gender-responsive budgeting in Indonesia. The study focuses on Kubu Raya and Mempawah Regencies in West Kalimantan Province, which were selected because they have adopted performance-based fiscal incentive policies through the Ecology Fiscal Transfer (EFT) scheme. Using a qualitative approach with the Gender Analysis Pathway (GAP), this study analyzes how these policies affect women's access, control, and benefits in village budget management. Data were obtained from policy documents, village financial reports, and technical assistance results from local governments. The research findings indicate that fiscal incentives encourage increased budget allocations for women's empowerment and strengthen women's substantive participation in development

planning. However, their effectiveness depends heavily on village institutional capacity and structural support from local governments. This study recommends strengthening the integration of GAP into village planning and budgeting to promote more gender-responsive policy reforms.

Keywords: Gender-responsive budgeting, EFT, GAP, Women's Empowerment, Village Budget

A. Introduction

Poverty in Indonesia remains multidimensional, with the poverty rate among women reaching 9.49% in 2023, slightly higher than that among men at 9.23% (BPS, 2023). This phenomenon confirms that systemic inequality, limited resources, and socio-cultural norms that restrict economic empowerment contribute to increasing the risk of poverty among women compared to men (Bradshaw, Chant, & Linneker, 2017). Other studies mention that poverty issues require solutions from both the central and regional governments through the implementation of regional autonomy in fiscal decentralization (Agatha & Uliansyah, 2021).

Unfortunately, in the structure of state and regional budgets, activities oriented towards women's empowerment are often included in the category of social or non-physical affairs, which are valued much lower than infrastructure and economic sectors. A study by *Badan Perencanaan Pembangunan Nasional* (Bappenas - National Development Planning Agency) shows that of the total national development budget, the portion of spending with gender budget tagging accounts for only 5-7% of ministries' and institutions' total expenditure (Bappenas, 2021). At the local level, particularly in villages, the budget for women's empowerment is often no more than 1% of the total Village Fund. Even in many villages, it is still merged into PKK activities or general training without clear gender equality

indicators (Kemenkeu, 2022).

This condition is also reflected in West Kalimantan Province, particularly in Kubu Raya and Mempawah Regencies. This has also resulted in low levels of active participation by women in economic and political life. This condition is supported by data showing that the Gender Empowerment Index (IDG) in Kubu Raya and Mempawah Regencies for 2020-2024 has remained stagnant below the national average.

Figure 1. Government Empowerment Index of Kubu Raya and Mempawah Regencies for 2020-2024

Source: Badan Pusat Statistik, 2025

The data above shows that the IDG of Kubu Raya Regency and Mempawah Regency in the 2020–2024 period shows a significant gap compared to the average of West Kalimantan Province and the Central Government. Kubu Raya Regency has a relatively high index score with an average of 73.88, despite experiencing a sharp decline in 2024 to 68.66 after reaching a peak of 77.63 in 2023. In contrast, Mempawah Regency shows lower, relatively stagnant achievement, with an average of 62.28, indicating the limited effectiveness of empowerment programs in the region. In comparison, the average for West Kalimantan Province (72.71) and the Central Government (76.86) indicates

that the position of the two regencies remains below the regional and national empowerment standards.

To address this issue, the Kubu Raya and Mempawah district governments implemented a performance incentive scheme for village governments based on the proportion of the budget in the village revenue and expenditure budget (APBDes) allocated to women's empowerment. This scheme is part of the adoption of the Ecology Fiscal Transfer (EFT) policy (EFT-Indonesia, 2025). This instrument was developed from the conventional fiscal transfer mechanism between levels of government by integrating environmental performance criteria into the fund allocation formula. This adoption has been stipulated in the regulations of the regents of both regions governing *Anggaran Dana Desa* (ADD - Village Fund Allocation) from 2022 to 2025. In Indonesia, the EFT policy has been implemented by 43 local governments, comprising 4 provinces, 36 regencies, and 3 city governments (EFT-Indonesia, 2025). This scheme is an extension of the fiscal transfer mechanism between governments, particularly between the central and regional governments, by incorporating certain considerations into the agreed allocation formula. The aim is to encourage regional governments to be more active in improving community welfare (Irawan, Tacconi, & Ring, 2014).

This study will focus on the Kubu Raya and Mempawah districts, which have implemented EFT policies from 2023 to 2025. These policies include performance incentives calculated based on the proportion of the women's empowerment budget at the village level. Kubu Raya and Mempawah Regencies were selected because they are regions that actively implement performance-based fiscal incentive policies that integrate women's empowerment indicators into village budget allocations (Firdaus et al., 2025).

Previous studies have confirmed that gender-responsive budgeting in Indonesia is still administrative and symbolic in nature. The implementation of gender-responsive budgeting

generally stops at the reporting stage through the Gender Analysis Pathway (GAP) and Gender Budget Statement (GBS) without producing structural changes in development planning (Hurriyati, Tjahjono, & Yamamoto, 2020).

Other studies further indicate that the implementation of gender-responsive budgeting (GRB) at the village level often remains limited in scope, particularly due to the lack of comprehensive strategies to strengthen institutional capacity and enhance women's meaningful participation. In many cases, GRB practices are implemented in a procedural manner without being accompanied by sustained efforts to build the technical skills and gender awareness of village officials or to empower women as active agents in planning and decision-making processes. As a result, women's involvement tends to be symbolic rather than substantive, reducing their influence on how development priorities are formulated and resources are allocated.

In addition, the structure of village expenditures has not yet been fully aligned to promote gender-inclusive poverty alleviation. Budget allocations frequently prioritize general or infrastructure-oriented programs, while initiatives specifically targeting women's economic empowerment and social protection remain marginal or insufficiently integrated. This imbalance reflects a broader challenge in translating gender policy commitments into concrete fiscal practices at the local level. Consequently, without deliberate efforts to integrate capacity-building mechanisms, participatory approaches, and gender-sensitive budget frameworks, the potential of village-level fiscal policies to address structural inequalities and support inclusive development outcomes remains underutilized (Agusta & Khoirunurrofik, 2024).

However, in the context of West Kalimantan – particularly in Kubu Raya and Mempawah Regencies – emerging dynamics can be observed through local government interventions, such as technical assistance, that encourage village administrations to

integrate gender equity principles into development planning and budget allocation. While existing studies on gender-responsive budgeting (GRB) in Indonesia have predominantly focused on procedural and administrative compliance, they have largely overlooked the role of performance-based fiscal incentives as instruments for driving structural transformation in village financial governance. Consequently, a critical research gap remains in understanding how local fiscal policies interact with institutional capacity to shape gender-responsive budgeting practices at the village level.

This study offers a novel contribution by examining the integration of performance-based fiscal incentives, particularly through the Ecology Fiscal Transfer (EFT) scheme, with a gender analytical framework in the context of village financial management. Unlike previous studies that tend to be descriptive, this research positions village fiscal policy as a strategic instrument for advancing gender equality by influencing budget allocation patterns, participatory mechanisms, and the distribution of development benefits. Methodologically, this study employs a qualitative descriptive approach, using the Gender Analysis Pathway (GAP) as the primary analytical tool. GAP is utilized to systematically assess gender disparities across four key dimensions: access, participation, control, and benefits in village budgeting processes (Nurhaeni & Sugarda, 2017).

Data collection was conducted through document analysis and in-depth interviews. Secondary data were obtained from policy documents, *Anggaran Pendapatan dan Belanja Desa* (APBDes - village financial reports), and records of technical assistance provided by local government agencies.

Meanwhile, primary data were collected through interviews with key informants at the regency level in two research locations: Kubu Raya Regency and Mempawah Regency. The informants consist of the Head of the Village Asset and Financial Division at the Office of Community and Village Empowerment, as well

as staff members within the relevant division who are directly involved in assisting village government officials in planning and budgeting processes. In total, this study involved eight informants, with four informants from each regency (one Head of Division and three technical staff members).

The informants were selected purposively based on their strategic roles, experience, and direct involvement in facilitating and overseeing the implementation of village budgeting policies. Data analysis was conducted interactively through the processes of data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing, while integrating the GAP framework to identify gender dynamics in village financial management.

Through this approach, the study aims to analyze how increased budget allocations for women's empowerment, facilitated by local government policies and institutional support, contribute to transforming village financial management practices. Theoretically, this article contributes to expanding the discourse on the intersection between fiscal decentralization and gender equality. Practically, it provides empirical insights to strengthen gender-responsive budgeting policies at the village level.

B. Discussion

1. Gender Responsive Budgeting and Village Governance

As part of the 2030 Agenda, sustainable development recognizes that gender parity is not only a fundamental human right but also a necessary foundation for a sustainable world (PBB, 2024). Therefore, recognizing the key role of budgets in closing the gender gap, governments at various levels in more than 80 countries have sought to incorporate a gender perspective into their budgeting processes (Kolovich & Loungani, 2018). Inequality still affects many important aspects of society,

including education, wages, and families. Countries around the world need to make continuous efforts to achieve a higher level of gender equality (Peng, Fu, & Zou, 2024).

Various studies have attempted to explain the success of gender-responsive budgeting initiatives, particularly in addressing whether gender-responsive budgeting can reduce existing inequalities and empower women. In response, existing research suggests that the success of gender-responsive budgeting lies in its integration into the government’s administrative routines (O’Hagan & Klatzer, 2018). As Rhonda Sharp pointed out, gender equality initiatives were never implemented because they were not part of the government’s budget decision-making process (Sharp, 2003).

In West Kalimantan Province, two regions have adopted performance-based incentive policies for village governments. One of the performance indicators calculated is the proportion of the women’s empowerment budget allocated by the village government. The following table shows the development of fiscal incentive policies in the two regions.

Table 1. Development of Fiscal Incentive Policies in Kubu Raya and Mempawah Regencies

Description	2023	2024	2025
Kubu Raya Regency			
Regent Regulation on ADD Allocation	Nomor 97/2022	Nomor 68/2023	Nomor 43/2024
Number of Incentive Recipients (Villages)	20	20	20

Nominal Incentive (Millions of Rupiah per village)	24,42	25,99	25,14
Total Number of Vil- lages	118	123	123
Mempawah Regency			
Regent Regulation on ADD Allocation	SK Bupati 110/2023	SK Bupati 69/2024	SK Bupati 35/2025
Number of Incentive Recipients (Villages)	20	20	20
Nominal Incentive (Millions of Rupiah per village)	28	32	37
Total Number of Vil- lages	60	60	60

Source: Researchers' Compilation, 2022-2025

In-depth research conducted from 2022 to 2024 found that villages receiving incentives from this policy allocated budgets for women's empowerment as one of the indicators assessed. The local government, through *Dinas Pemberdayaan Masyarakat dan Desa* (DPMDes - the Community Empowerment and Village Government Agency), has implemented a technical assistance approach in the preparation of the Village Work Plan (RKPDes) and Village Budget (APBDes) based on the principles of village governance. This approach introduces the dimensions of social and environmental justice in village budgeting, including incentives for

activities that support women’s capacity building in the economic and social sectors.

Figure 2. Development of Village Governance in Kubu Raya and Mempawah Districts

Source: Fiscal Incentive Policy Assessment Matrix in Kubu Raya and Mempawah, 2025

Since its implementation, the data collected shows that around 70% of villages (out of a total of 123 villages) in Kubu Raya have achieved good village governance in planning. Meanwhile, in Mempawah, 90% of villages tend to maintain positive governance.

In villages that have implemented good village financial management, calculations are also made on the proportion of the women’s empowerment budget sourced from village funds. These calculations are carried out through *Sistem Keuangan Desa* (Siskeudes - the Village Financial System) in both districts. This

system monitors the allocation and implementation of the women’s empowerment budget, as recorded in the community development and community empowerment columns.

Figure 3. Proportion of Women’s Empowerment Budget Based on APBDes in Kubu Raya and Mempawah Districts (in millions)

Source: Village Financial System in Kubu Raya and Mempawah Districts, 2025

The findings confirm that the consistency of villages in complying with the schedule for preparing the Village Budget (APBDes) and submitting the Village Work Plan (RKPDDes) is directly proportional to an increase in budget allocations for women’s empowerment. The planning and budgeting process, accompanied by adequate assistance and guidance, also encourages village governments to allocate a larger proportion of the budget to women’s empowerment programs.

This study highlights conditions in the Kubu Raya and Mempawah districts that require more intensive coordination between village governments and the Community Empowerment and Village Government Agency (DPMDes). Based on field findings, the process of drafting and finalizing APBDes and RKPDes documents in both districts is generally concentrated in three months at the end of the current fiscal year. During this period, village governments draft and adjust the planning (RKPDes) and budgeting (APBDes) through established mechanisms. Subsequently, revisions and coordination are carried out on any parts that are not yet in accordance, before finally inputting them into the Village Financial System (Siskeudes) for APBDes and finalizing RKPDes.

On the other hand, DPMDes plays a crucial role not only as a technical facilitator but also as an institutional intermediary bridging district-level policy directives with implementation practices at the village level. Through structured support, DPMDes ensures that village governments can interpret regulatory frameworks, align their planning documents with policy priorities, and integrate performance indicators—particularly those related to gender responsiveness—into budgeting processes. This function becomes especially important in villages with limited administrative capacity, where technical guidance significantly influences the quality and consistency of planning and budgeting outputs.

Furthermore, the verification and validation stage conducted by DPMDes serves as a critical governance mechanism to ensure accountability and coherence across policy instruments. This process does not merely involve administrative checking, but also a substantive

assessment of whether budget allocations reflect identified needs, align with development priorities, and meet the criteria of performance-based incentive policies. By ensuring consistency across planning documents, budget structures, and policy indicators, DPMDes helps strengthen the integrity of village financial management systems. In this regard, its role extends beyond supervision toward fostering institutional learning and promoting more standardized, transparent, and gender-responsive governance practices across villages.

This effort marks a paradigm shift from project-based budgeting to performance-based budgeting and gender equity. One of the fundamental flaws in Indonesia's fiscal decentralization policy is the tendency to emphasize nominal equity without accounting for heterogeneity in local needs (Lewis, 2015). Meanwhile, research on the same budget context shows that the effectiveness of Village Funds in reducing poverty is greatly influenced by the structure of spending and the institutional capacity of villages (Agusta & Khoirunurrofik, 2024). Thus, the contexts of Kubu Raya and Mempawah provide empirical space to examine how gender-responsive budgeting can be translated into village-level fiscal mechanisms through district-level institutional interventions.

2. Analysis of Changes in Governance and Women's Participation

The transformation of village financial management in these two regions is not only reflected in increased budget allocations for women's empowerment, but also

in changes to participation mechanisms. The results of the study show that in several villages in Kubu Raya, for example, *musrenbang* (thematic village deliberation forums) specifically for women, children, and people with disabilities have begun to open up space for women's groups to propose productive economic programs and community leadership training. This practice demonstrates a shift from symbolic participation to substantive participation (DP3KB, 2025).

From a governance theory perspective, this change is a manifestation of the shift in power relations in the local policy process (Agusta & Khoirunurrofik, 2024). Although still limited, the presence of female actors in budget planning and oversight reinforces the principle of inclusive governance. This finding enriches the discourse on GRB, which has been criticized for being stuck in an administrative approach (Fithriyah, 2020). On the other hand, challenges remain in the form of cultural resistance, limited budget literacy, and weak gender-based oversight mechanisms. Thus, the dynamics in Kubu Raya and Mempawah indicate a transition towards more gender-responsive village governance, in which fiscal and social aspects are beginning to be linked in a mutually reinforcing policy ecosystem.

The findings of this study make two important contributions. First, academically, the study's results reinforce the theory that the effectiveness of gender-responsive budgeting at the local level is largely determined by institutional capacity and structural support from local governments. The integration of gender-responsive fiscal policies at the village level cannot be optimally implemented without technical

assistance, evaluation mechanisms, and gender-sensitive performance indicators (Bank, 2021). Second, in practical terms, this study shows that increasing the budget allocation for women's empowerment can be an instrument for strengthening more participatory governance if it is accompanied by a transformation of women's social values and roles in village institutions. This confirms the importance of developing a fiscal assistance model that integrates social, economic, and ecological justice, as applied in the fiscal incentive policy approach in West Kalimantan.

Thus, this discussion shows that village fiscal policy is not only an economic instrument but also a social arena that determines the direction of gender transformation at the grassroots level. In the future, further research is needed to examine the relationship between local fiscal innovation and the strengthening of the women's empowerment index, so that the results can provide an empirical basis for formulating more gender-inclusive national policies.

The findings of this study make two important contributions, both academic and practical. From an academic perspective, the results reinforce the argument that the effectiveness of gender-responsive budgeting at the local level is largely determined by institutional capacity and structural support from local governments. However, this finding cannot be uniformly generalized across all villages in Kubu Raya and Mempawah Regencies. Empirical data indicate that approximately 70% of villages in Kubu Raya and 90% in Mempawah demonstrate improvements in planning governance and budget allocation for women's empowerment. In contrast,

the remaining villages continue to face limitations in administrative and technical capacity.

These differences are particularly evident in villages that receive consistent technical assistance from the Village Community Empowerment and Governance Agency (DPMDes), which tend to produce more structured planning documents (RKPDes) and budgeting processes (APBDes) that explicitly incorporate gender indicators. In contrast, villages with limited technical support or lower institutional capacity tend to maintain conventional budgeting practices that are not yet fully gender-responsive.

Thus, the effectiveness of integrating gender-responsive fiscal policies at the village level depends not only on the existence of such policies but also on the availability of technical assistance, evaluation mechanisms, and institutionalized gender-sensitive performance indicators within village planning and budgeting systems. This finding highlights that the relationship between institutional capacity and policy effectiveness is inherently contextual and varies across villages, rather than representing a homogeneous condition.

From a practical perspective, this study demonstrates that increasing budget allocations for women's empowerment can serve as a strategic instrument to strengthen more participatory governance. However, the impact also varies across villages, with only those with more inclusive forms of women's participation—such as *musrenbang* (thematic village deliberation forums) or the active engagement of women's groups able to translate increased budget allocations into substantive changes in decision-making processes.

This suggests that the transformation driven by gender-responsive budgeting is not solely fiscal in nature but also social, particularly in reshaping women's roles and positions within village institutions. Therefore, the development of fiscal incentive policies should incorporate an integrated approach that combines social, economic, and ecological dimensions of justice, as reflected in the policy approach adopted in West Kalimantan.

Overall, this discussion demonstrates that village fiscal policy serves not only as an economic instrument but also as a social arena that shapes the trajectory of grassroots gender transformation. However, given the variation in implementation across villages, further research—particularly comparative and quantitative studies—is needed to systematically examine the relationship between local fiscal innovation and improvements in the Gender Empowerment Index. Such efforts would provide a stronger empirical foundation for formulating more gender-inclusive national policies.

To further substantiate this argument, the variation in outcomes across villages also indicates that fiscal policy alone is insufficient to drive gender transformation without parallel investments in institutional learning and governance quality. Villages that demonstrate stronger outcomes are not merely those with higher budget allocations, but those that can internalize gender-responsive principles into their planning routines and decision-making culture. This suggests that the effectiveness of gender-responsive budgeting is deeply embedded in the interplay between policy design and local institutional dynamics. Therefore, strengthening local governance capacity, ensuring continuity of

technical assistance, and embedding gender-sensitive accountability mechanisms are critical preconditions for scaling up the impact of fiscal incentives beyond isolated cases toward more systemic and sustainable gender equality outcomes.

3. Gender-Responsive Budgeting Analysis through the Gender Analysis Pathway (GAP)

Gender-responsive budgeting in this study is analyzed using the *Gender Analysis Pathway (GAP)*, a widely recognized analytical framework in public policy studies for identifying and assessing gender disparities in development planning and budgeting processes. GAP serves not only as a diagnostic tool but also as a systematic framework for evaluating the extent to which public policies substantively and equitably accommodate women's needs and interests (Budlender & Hewitt, 2002; Elson, 2006).

In this research, GAP is applied to examine the implementation of performance-based fiscal incentives through the Ecology Fiscal Transfer (EFT) scheme in the context of village financial management. Conceptually, this framework encompasses four key dimensions: access, participation, control, and benefits. The access dimension refers to the extent to which women have opportunities to participate in development programs and access resources. Participation captures women's involvement in planning and decision-making processes, particularly within *musrenbang*. Control relates to women's capacity to influence strategic decisions and resource allocation, while benefits refer to the tangible outcomes that women receive from implemented policies and programs.

This multidimensional approach enables a more comprehensive analysis that goes beyond women's mere presence in development processes, focusing instead on the distribution of power and development outcomes. This perspective aligns with the broader literature, which emphasizes that the effectiveness of gender-responsive budgeting depends not only on budget allocation but also on transforming power relations and ensuring the equitable distribution of benefits (O'Hagan & Klatzer, 2018; Sharp, 2003).

Empirically, the GAP framework is applied through the analysis of village planning documents (*RKPD*s) and budget documents (*APBD*s), as well as participatory practices in village deliberation forums in Kubu Raya and Mempawah Regencies. The findings indicate that performance-based fiscal incentives have increased budget allocations for women's empowerment; however, their impacts vary across the four GAP dimensions.

In terms of access, women have gained greater opportunities to participate in economic empowerment programs and capacity-building initiatives. Nevertheless, access remains uneven across villages, particularly in those with limited institutional capacity. Regarding participation, there has been a notable increase in women's involvement in village planning forums. However, in several cases, participation remains dominated by local elites, limiting its representativeness and inclusiveness.

In the dimension of control, women have begun to engage in discussions related to village budgeting, yet their influence over strategic decision-making remains limited. This suggests that participation is still largely procedural rather than substantive. Meanwhile, in the benefits dimension, increased budget allocations have

supported the expansion of women-focused economic programs. However, the actual impact on women's welfare has not been systematically measured due to the absence of gender-sensitive evaluation indicators.

These findings demonstrate that increased budget allocation for women's empowerment does not automatically translate into substantive gender equality. The effectiveness of gender-responsive budgeting depends on the simultaneous integration of all four GAP dimensions, supported by adequate institutional capacity and affirmative policy measures from local governments. This is consistent with broader empirical findings indicating that the success of gender budgeting initiatives is strongly influenced by institutional factors, including bureaucratic capacity and political commitment (Kolovich, 2018).

Furthermore, the GAP analysis underscores the need to complement fiscal incentive policies with institutional strengthening strategies and gender-sensitive performance indicators. Local governments should integrate the GAP framework throughout the entire village planning and budgeting cycle, from problem identification to policy evaluation. In addition, the development of gender-based monitoring systems within village financial management platforms, such as Siskeudes, is essential to ensure that budget allocations are not only increased quantitatively but also generate measurable impacts on gender equality.

The application of the Gender Analysis Pathway (GAP) in this study offers not only a comprehensive analytical framework but also a policy-oriented approach to advancing gender-responsive budgeting at the village

level. By systematically examining the dimensions of access, participation, control, and benefits, GAP enables a deeper understanding of how fiscal policies shape gender relations beyond mere budget allocations. This approach highlights that gender equality is not solely a matter of increasing financial resources, but also of ensuring equitable distribution of opportunities, decision-making power, and development outcomes.

Furthermore, the findings underscore the potential of village fiscal policy as a strategic instrument for fostering gender equality within the broader context of fiscal decentralization and local governance. The integration of gender considerations into fiscal incentive mechanisms, such as the Ecology Fiscal Transfer (EFT), demonstrates how local policy innovation can influence institutional behavior and promote more inclusive governance practices. However, the effectiveness of such policies depends on adequate institutional capacity, sustained technical assistance, and gender-sensitive monitoring systems that can translate policy intentions into measurable outcomes.

In addition, GAP analysis reveals that gender transformation in village governance requires a multidimensional approach that connects fiscal policy with social and institutional change. Without strengthening local governance structures and embedding gender-responsive principles into routine planning and budgeting processes, the impact of fiscal interventions will remain limited and uneven. Therefore, integrating GAP into the full cycle of village financial management – from planning and budgeting to implementation and evaluation – becomes essential for ensuring that gender-

responsive budgeting contributes to long-term, systemic change. This reinforces the importance of aligning fiscal decentralization policies with broader gender equality agendas to achieve more inclusive and sustainable development outcomes at the grassroots level.

C. Conclusion

This study shows that implementing performance-based fiscal incentive policies in Kubu Raya and Mempawah districts has effectively increased the proportion of the women's empowerment budget at the village level through a village financial management approach. The integration of gender-responsive budgeting principles into the Ecology Fiscal Transfer (EFT) scheme encourages a shift in women's participation from symbolic to substantive, making villages more inclusive in development planning and budgeting.

Overall, the study's result confirm that the success of gender-responsive budgeting at the local level is strongly influenced by institutional capacity, technical assistance, and local government commitment. Gender-equitable village fiscal policies have proven to be a strategic instrument for strengthening participatory governance and accelerating social transformation towards gender equality in rural areas.

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